

RECYCLING, COMPOSITES, AND DESIGN
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ABSTRACT

Materials disposal issues must be confronted by the composites community. Composites disposal is explored from three related aspects: recycling, composites themselves, and design. All are examined from the vantage point of the automotive industry. The magnitude of the composites disposal problem and its relation to the total plastics situation are discussed. Categories of recycling are established. The special problems of the auto industry are briefly reviewed. The abilities and shortcomings of various recycling technologies are reviewed, along with potential markets for recycled products. A brief review of composites in the auto industry is related to materials disposal issues. Recycling challenges for automotive composites are discussed. Trends in automotive materials and applications are related to disposal difficulties. The design aspect is used to integrate composites and recycling, through the suggestion of a set of eleven design for recycling heuristics. Tradeoffs between "recyclability" and other factors are briefly described. Metrics for design for recycling are suggested.

KEYWORDS: Recycling; Composites; Design

1. INTRODUCTION

There can be little doubt that materials disposal issues represent some of the most important challenges faced by the composites community, including materials suppliers, fabricators, and end users. Why is it that composites disposal is such a pressing concern? The answer involves a combination of growing environmental awareness among consumers (both informed and uninformed), increasing competitiveness among materials systems, and the life cycle costs of engineering systems. These factors are compounded by technological problems. The presence of one or more reinforcing phases often makes composites significantly more difficult to reprocess than "monolithic" materials such as steel, aluminum, and polyethylene.

Because of the tremendous volumes of material it consumes, the automotive industry is used throughout this paper in discussing the various issues. The automotive industry currently consumes about 25 weight % of all fiber and/or particulate reinforced plastics (hereafter referred to as composites) (1). The total amount of composites used in autos and the fraction of total auto weight made up of composites are both steadily increasing and could go much higher. Environmental awareness is attracting increasing attention to automobile disposal. With today's technology, as the amount of composites (and other non-metals as well) in cars increases, so does the amount of material that must be landfilled. Disposal of these materials could have a significant impact on several markets. This paper reviews and discusses composites disposal issues from the interrelated viewpoints of recycling, the composites themselves, and the design process.

2. RECYCLING

William Rathje argues that there are only four fundamental ways of dealing with waste of any kind. It can be burned, buried, reused, or we can use less of it in the first place (source reduction) (2). Which of these four methods (or what combinations of them) constitute "recycling"? For some people, only "reuse" is considered recycling. Others consider various forms of "burning" to be recycling, provided there is an energy return and/or the by-products of the process are useful. Few consider "burying" to be recycling. "Source reduction" is the too-often neglected member of Rathje's quartet. Source reduction may not be "recycling" per se, but its significance should not be underestimated since it cures the problem and not the symptoms of solid waste. The processes reviewed in Section 2.5 focus on "reuse" and "burning" technologies, or various combinations of the two.

2.1 The Total Plastics Picture Recently, national attention has focused on disposal and recycling of unreinforced polymers. In the United States plastics constitute roughly 8% by weight and 25% by volume, of the approximately 160×10^9 kg of municipal solid waste (MSW) generated per year (3). However, only 1% by weight of discarded plastic products was being recycled as of 1989 (4). MSW includes durable goods, or items designed to have service lives greater than three years (automobiles, computers, appliances, etc.), and consumables, products such as packaging that are used once or a few times and then discarded. In 1988, the transportation industry consumed 7-8 weight % of the total amount of plastics generated in the United States (5).

Where do composites fit into the total plastics figure? The data in Figure 1 are revealing. While total plastics production in the United States is approaching 25×10^9 kg (6) and increasing, the total for composites (fiber or particulate reinforced thermosetting and thermoplastic polymers) is steady at about 1×10^9 kg (1), or about 4% of the total plastics mass. A breakdown of the composites total is included in Section 3.

Figure 1 Comparison of reinforced plastics to total plastics production in the U.S.

2.2 The Automotive Industry On average, automobiles remain in service for ten years (7). About 80% of all automobiles (8) are "recycled", typically as follows: The condition of the automobile when it no longer has value as an auto, along with its make, model, and model year, dictate how much of the car's components will be removed for resale. Dismantlers remove components such as tires, batteries, trunk lids, hoods, doors, and transmissions. Once these saleable items have been removed the remaining auto hulk is typically sent to an

automobile shredder. In the shredding process, the hulk is reduced in a hammer mill to pieces with no dimension larger than about 15 cm. Auto shredder residue (ASR) is the fraction of material remaining after the separation of saleable ferrous and nonferrous metals from the shredded auto. ASR consists mainly of polymers, glass, fabric, dirt and other contaminating debris. The average hulk (processed in 1990) consisted of about 1000 kg of ferrous metals, 70 kg of non-ferrous metals, and 350 kg of ASR. Approximately 5×10^9 kg of auto shredder residue (ASR) are disposed of each year (9). This figure is certain to increase, since the cars being shredded today are about ten years old and the fraction of non-metals has risen steadily since that time. Currently, ASR is a liability to the shredder and must be landfilled. Stable shredder operation currently depends on iron and steel recovery (10). A combination of vehicle size reduction and substitution of lighter weight materials have decreased the gross weight of vehicles, while increasing the fraction of ASR (11). Thus the shredder industry is being squeezed two ways and faces economic catastrophe. In this respect, composites recycling is seen (along with recycling the rest of ASR) as a serious concern.

Materials disposal regulations will soon affect every aspect of the transportation sector. These regulations could range from deposits on batteries, tires and motor oil, to bans on certain "non-recyclable" materials. Some would include composites in this latter category (12)!

2.3 Categorizing Recycling Rathje's "reuse" and "burning" categories for waste disposal can be more descriptively categorized as primary, secondary, tertiary, and quaternary recycling (13). Primary recycling is reprocessing waste into its original use or comparable products. The recycling of aluminum beverage cans is an outstanding example of primary recycling. Recycling polyethylene terephthalate (PET) scrap from discarded bottles into new bottles is a potential example of primary recycling from the world of polymers (pending U.S. Food and Drug Administration approval). In secondary recycling, or degraded reuse, materials are processed and used in applications not requiring virgin material properties. The current markets for recycled PET, such as carpet backing, fall into this category. Tertiary recycling is energy recovery, while quaternary is chemical recovery. The pyrolysis of sheet molding compound (SMC), described below, is a form of tertiary and quaternary recycling. With time, pyrolysis could include elements of secondary recycling. "Source reduction" can occur two ways: by using less material (lighter cars) and by making products that last longer.

2.4 Recycling, Conservation and the Environment Recycling polymers represents conservation of a non-renewable natural resource. In the hydrocarbon life cycle, Figure 2, non-renewable resources are extracted and refined into fuels and non-fuels. The fuel stream accounts for 86% of hydrocarbons consumed. Non-fuels or petrochemicals represent only 14% of the hydrocarbon stream. Petrochemicals include plastics, synthetic fibers, solvents, lubricants, detergents, paints, and other products (14). Petrochemicals can be disposed of, in Rathje's terms, by burning, burying, or reusing them. Just as composites represent a small fraction of the total plastics stream, plastics represent a small fraction of the hydrocarbon stream. In terms of resource conservation, then, the recycling of reinforced plastics has extremely limited utility compared to source reduction of fuels or recycling of unreinforced plastics. However, as the auto shredder example shows, there are other reasons to recycle composites.

With 80% of existing landfills predicted to close in the next 20 years due to stiffer government regulations, public opposition, and diminishing capacity of older landfills (15), the pressure to recycle intensifies. Despite research into numerous alternatives, landfilling remains the only practical method of ASR disposal.

2.5 Recycling Technologies This section briefly reviews recycling processes potentially applicable to composites. Table 1 summarizes each of the recycling technologies discussed.

2.5.1 Pyrolysis Pyrolysis involves thermal decomposition of organic materials at high temperatures in the absence of oxygen. Attempts to recycle cured SMC in-house manufacturing scraps are in early stages. By January 1990, three trial SMC pyrolysis runs had been completed at a converted tire pyrolysis facility (16). In this process shredded SMC is fed to a furnace where it is pyrolyzed at 400°C-550°C. The end products are fuel gas (which can be used to sustain the pyrolysis process), an oil-like substance, and a solid consisting mainly of

Figure 2 The hydrocarbon life cycle

calcium carbonate and glass. Efforts have concentrated on substituting the solid by-product for calcium carbonate in SMC. The solid by-product must be burned to remove residual carbon and then ground to a fine particle size. Because calcium carbonate is so inexpensive (\$0.11/kg.-\$0.14/kg.), the economics of substitution are uncertain. Not surprisingly, the cost of grinding the solid by-product goes up as the mean particle size goes down. Despite this encouraging work, there are several other unresolved issues including the ability to shred feed material to the proper size, capability of processing combined uncured and cured SMC scrap parts, uses for recovered pyrolysis oil, and recycling scrapped auto parts as opposed to in-house SMC scrap (16).

2.5.2 Hydrolysis Recycling through hydrolysis is better suited for recovery of monomers of materials manufactured by polyaddition and polycondensation reactions. Polymers capable of recycling through hydrolysis include polyurethanes, polyesters, and polyamides (17). Success of this process requires the scrap materials to be separated by polymer type, and is thus not applicable to unseparated ASR (18).

2.5.3 Incineration ASR has been substituted for fossil fuel in, for example, cement mills. Poor cement quality results from shredder waste feed difficulties and chlorine contamination. The Japanese have suggested separating the combustible portions of ASR, mixing with resin, and compressing the mixture into briquettes (18). A German plant incinerates plastics from car batteries in pure oxygen. A similar process proposes use of steam generated from incineration with oxygen as an energy source for a shredding mill (18). Most ASR incineration schemes would require flue gas scrubbers.

2.5.4 Recycling polyurethane scrap Developmental work on recycling reaction injection molded polyurethane automotive scrap is ongoing. One technique involves molding approximately 10% regrind as filler in other molding processes (9). Compression molding of these materials is limited to simple shapes and requires very high pressures. The Polyurethanes Recycle & Recovery Council plans to establish a pilot facility to develop tertiary recycling (9).

2.5.5 Recycling phenolic scrap Phenolic scraps containing glass fibers or carbon fibers are claimed, by phenolic suppliers, to be capable of being pulverized into particulates and used as fillers and extender in molding compounds (19).

Table 1 Summary of Recycling Technologies

Process	Pyrolysis (16)	Hydrolysis (17,18)	Incineration (18)	Incineration in pure O ₂ (18)	RIM regrind (9)	Phenolic regrind (19)
Feedstock (current)	in-house SMC scrap	flexible foam	mixed polymeric waste	plastic scrap from auto batteries	in-house scrap RIM PU (polyurethane)	phenolic scrap parts
Feedstock (potential)	post-consumer SMC	rigid foams, elastomers, and RIM resin	ASR	ASR	post-consumer RIM products	other thermoset regrind
Products	fuel gas, oil, inorganic solid	monomers of the input material	heat, solid residue	heat, solid residue	ground particles	ground phenolic and fillers
Strengths	energy self-sustaining, potential for reuse of solid residue	recovered monomers can be reused	energy recycling	smaller reactors, reduced facility costs, less pollution	mixing with thermoplastic PU allows some thermal forming	may improve properties of some molding compounds
Weaknesses	scrap feed size economics	inputs must be separated into material types	air pollution, public distrust	requires air separation plant	limited forming, market demand	regrind cost, market demand
Notes	questions remain re: processing solid residue in SMC	best for polyurethanes		cost 30% less than a comparable modern refuse incinerator	unproven mechanical properties	benefits from regrind depend on filler and amount of regrind

2.6 Markets for Recycled Composites The availability of markets for any kind of recycled product is a prime consideration. A balance must be achieved between demand limited and supply limited market extremes (3). Even the most cost efficient and technically advanced recycling process will quickly fail if there is insufficient demand for its end products. The example of recycled newsprint is instructive. Recycled newsprint in the U.S. went from a \$12-\$25 per thousand kg commodity to a huge surplus that had to be disposed of at a cost of \$5-\$20 per thousand kg (20). The flooded market forced several newsprint collectors out of business. At the other extreme, recyclers of products such as aluminum cans are challenged with satisfying strong demand. Manufacturers naturally prefer recycled goods if costs are competitive with virgin material and quality is not compromised. Developing large and stable markets for recycled ASR must be a prime research goal.

3. COMPOSITES

3.1 Composites in the Automobile In Section 2.1, the relation of composites production to total plastics production was discussed. It is also important to consider the uses and types of composites currently being produced. Figure 3 shows the total weight of composites produced (1) along with the weight of SMC (21) and "advanced composites" prepreg (22) for comparison.

The figure shows, unsurprisingly, that disposal issues for prepreg (traditionally an aerospace material) are certainly not driven by production volume. More surprising perhaps is the low fraction of composites production made up of SMC (96×10^6 kg in 1989 or about 8% of the total). Even within the automotive industry, SMC comprises only about one third of total composites use (21, 22). A large percentage of the remainder undoubtedly consists of a wide variety of particulate and/or fiber reinforced injection moldings.

Over the past thirty years polymers, of which composites are a subset, have gradually established niches in automobile production, increasing from 1.5 - 3.5 weight % of the average car weight in 1960 to 10 - 15 % in 1990 (23). Today, composites account for about 2-4 weight % of all the materials in cars. Composite have been roughly estimated to save a kilogram for every kilogram used (11). This savings accrues through improved specific mechanical properties and through parts consolidation. The latter is the ability of advanced materials

Figure 3 SMC and prepreg production versus total "reinforced plastics" production in U.S.

systems of one or relatively few parts to replace steel assemblies consisting of large numbers of parts. In addition to reducing weight, parts consolidation reduces assembly costs while vehicle function (reduced noise, vibration and harshness) is improved (24) (25). Consumers are often attracted to the radical styling offered by composite exterior automotive body panels. Currently, steel body panels are limited in design flexibility due to their formability characteristics (26). Other advantages associated with composites include resistance to corrosion and lower tooling cost. The latter often allows composites to be cost effective for low to intermediate volume production runs (27).

Each of General Motor's three versions of their 1990 All Purpose Van uses over 150 kg of SMC (5). The estimated annual production of this vehicle is 225,000 (28). This represents almost one-third of the 1989 SMC production total. Other examples of composite use include Ford's SMC tailgates and hoods on their Aerostar minivans and of course the fiberglass shell of GM's Corvette.

Automotive composite applications are dominated by glass fiber reinforcement and by the extensive use of low cost inert fillers such as calcium carbonate. For example, typical SMC formulations consist of 46 weight % calcium carbonate, 28 % glass, and 26 % polyester resin and additives (30).

Exterior composite body panels are a well-established application. Horizontal automotive body panels of SMC are common. For vertical body panels (where less stiffness is usually required) various thermoplastics and thermoplastic composites (such as reaction injection molded thermoplastic polyurethanes (28) and thermoplastic polyesters (31) are beginning to compete with SMC.

Auto experts are questioning where the next weight savings in automobiles will come from. One comments that "All the easy parts have been found" (29).

One of the largest relatively untapped markets for composites in automobiles is structural components. For instance, Ford is developing a two piece high speed resin transfer molded front structure to replace the Escort's 90 piece steel front structure (25). Many other automotive structural components are being redesigned for composites (32). E-glass fibers are likely to reinforce these parts, in a matrix of either polyester or vinyl ester.

Leaf springs and drive shafts are two composite structural components that are presently in service. Ford annually installs about 3000 drive shafts filament wound of graphite and E-glass fibers in a polyester resin for their Econoline van. It is estimated that General Motors annually uses 600,000 glass fiber reinforced leaf springs in their Corvette and other models (24).

3.2 Recycling Challenges Potential techniques for recycling ASR were described in Section 2. As noted there is much work to be done. Widely scattered material properties can be attributed to ASR composition variability (33), polymer degradation, and contamination by foreign matter. The variability of ASR may be increased since shredders are often used to dispose of miscellaneous objects such as large appliances (34). Separation of ASR into its constituent components is economically questionable with current technology. Studies conducted through the Plastic Institute of America show that ASR can be recycled by extrusion and injection molding techniques (33). Variability of properties (in part due to feedstock variability) currently limits such parts to low performance applications such as park benches, composite board (mixture of auto scrap and wood chips) (35), and outdoor decorative articles (33).

The inherent ability of thermoplastics to be reprocessed allows at least the potential for primary recycling. The cross-linked structure of thermosets typically limits its prospects to secondary, tertiary, and quaternary recycling. However, for both thermosetting and thermoplastic composites, the presence of second and third phases (fibers and fillers) complicates recycling technology. Thermoplastic composites primary recycling is hindered by degradation of the reinforcement phase, of the fiber/matrix interface, and of the polymer itself (13). Carbon/PEEK laminate scrap has been successfully chopped up and compression molded with resulting properties rivaling virgin short fiber composites (36).

Work continues on processes for recovering fibers from various forms of composites. One pilot plant employs the calcining process to recover woven glass fibers from scrap edge trimmings and reject panels of glass/epoxy circuit boards (37). A complex milling, heating, and chemical treating process extracts woven patches of fibers 0.1 - 0.3 cm in diameter. The fibers are said to suffer no significant loss in mechanical properties.

Because of fiber costs, recovery of graphite fibers is far more attractive than for glass. Complexity of carbon fiber recovery and costs increase as follows: loose fibers or tows, fabrics, uncured prepreg scrap, and cured laminates (38). Solvents have been used to recover fiber from uncured epoxy prepreg scrap. These fibers have been used in aligned short fiber non-woven fabrics. Fiber recovery from cured laminates through thermochemical degradation has been attempted but many problems remain (38).

3.3 Metals versus Composites in Automobiles Even before we consider materials disposal issues, composites face stiff challenges from metals for the lighter and smaller vehicles of tomorrow. Many experts believe steel will continue to dominate automotive structural applications (26). High strength structural steels and steel sheet compete well with composites in terms of cost effective manufacturing, strength, formability, and weight reduction. Economically, steels are currently better suited for very high production volumes than composites. However, lower tooling costs make composites attractive for low to intermediate volume applications (39). Aluminum also competes with composites to some extent. Although aluminum is now mostly limited to low volume/high cost vehicles, in its favor are its adaptability to current vehicle manufacturing methods as compared to composites and favorable energy absorption characteristics (40). As the importance of materials disposal grows, proven recycling (reuse) technology and the existence of stable markets for recycled metals is currently a strong factor in favor of metals.

4. DESIGN

4.1 "Design for Recycling" Design may be defined as the information needed to create, use, and dispose of a product (41). "Recyclability" is a major new "customer want": it must be designed for. The term recyclability is much more than the technological ability of a product to be recycled, or in Rathje's terms, reused. Recyclability encompasses ease of product recovery through disassembly or separation, product performance/acceptance, market availability, disposal of non-recoverables remaining after recycling, and recycling incentives/expenditures (42). Based on our definition of design, a step in the design process is often omitted. Closing the design loop forces consideration of product disposal. This requires collaboration of the raw material manufacturer, the molder/converter, end user industry, the consumer, and the waste disposal industry (23). "Design for Recycling" is the latest in a seemingly endless stream of "Design for X" strategies. All such schemes must be viewed with skepticism because the wide range of requirements for any given product precludes the luxury of designing solely for one particular need. However, certain tentative design principles can be suggested as a first step in adding disposal issues to the design process.

4.2 Design for Recycling Heuristics These heuristics are intended to be general guidelines for design, to stimulate discussion, and to serve as benchmarks for future design for recycling work.

1. The longer an engineered system lasts and the less materials it uses, the better (things will be, strictly in materials disposal terms).

This heuristic underscores the value of source reduction as a recycling tool. The true value of composites in materials disposal terms may lie primarily in source reduction. If composites-intensive cars last longer and use less material, the impact on materials disposal will be significant.

2. The easier it is to separate parts of different materials at the end of service the better.

This heuristic summarizes the need for design for disassembly techniques. Germany appears to be the leader in this technology (43). Engineers at BMW and Volkswagen meticulously disassemble scrapped autos, record the process, and make design changes to allow easier disassembly of next generation automobiles. Designing for disassembly reduces identification time, labor, and the number of materials in an engineered system (thus decreasing the amount and variability of ASR).

3. The fewer materials used in an engineered system the better.

The automotive industry has incorporated a tremendous variety of materials into vehicle design to satisfy a wide range of customer wants. This proliferation of materials has increased the complexity and precarious economics

of the already difficult auto recycling process. As developed earlier, a major difficulty with recycling ASR is its variability. As a feedstock for a recycling process, this variability makes it difficult to work with. A reduction in the number of materials used in autos would tend to improve this situation.

4. The fewer components within a given material in an engineered system the better.

Similarly to heuristic two above, fewer components within these materials increases the potential to recycle. By definition, composites are less desirable than monolithic materials in terms of this heuristic.

5. The easier the components of a material are to separate (if there is more than one component) the better.

If a material can be reused at the part level, then heuristic 5 doesn't apply (see heuristics 9 and 10).

6. The more energy and/or useful materials that can be recovered from a component the better.

7. The less impact on air, land, and water resources that the recovery process makes the better.

8. The less energy and materials that must be expended in the recovery process the better.

Heuristics 6-8 can be combined into the following expression:

$$RC = (M_{sav} + M_{rec} - M_{exp}) + (E_{sav} + E_{rec} - E_{exp}) - I \quad (1)$$

where RC is recycling cost, E_{sav} and M_{sav} are the energy and materials saved (or lost) due to the substitution of the material (with respect to the material it replaced), E_{rec} and M_{rec} are the energy and materials recovered through the recycling process, E_{exp} and M_{exp} are the energy and materials expended in the recycling process, and I is the environmental impact of the material's life cycle. All quantities are measured in monetary units.

9. Parts or subsystems that have intrinsic value are better than those that must be torn down and separated with the rest of the system.

10. The more universal the utility of a materials system is, the better.

Materials in an engineered system should be designed for adaptability to multiple applications. Unreinforced thermoplastics recyclers take advantage of this in their efforts to recycle PET, polyethylene, polypropylene and polystyrene.

11. The fewer "secondary operations" required for a given materials system, the better.

Secondary operations here include priming, painting, joining, etc. The materials used in such operations are themselves difficult to reuse, and they can complicate the recovery process for the primary systems they are applied to (per heuristic 3). Composites and monolithic polymers are sometimes able to take advantage of this heuristic, particularly if these materials can be used in the uncoated condition.

Some of these heuristics (particularly numbers 1-5 and 9) are summarized in Figure 4, which shows the various levels at which an engineered system can be recycled. These are related to Rathje's and Liedner's categories at the left of the figure.

It is axiomatic in design that when something is gained something else is usually lost. What do we give up to get "recyclability"? A car that is "designed for disassembly" might be easier for thieves to strip. A car with comparatively few materials (per heuristic 2) might perform poorly compared to one with hundreds of highly

specialized materials, carefully refined for individual applications. The heuristics above do not operate in a vacuum.

4.3 The "Metrics" of Design for Recycling When considering a major new "customer want" such as "recyclability" it is important to develop parameters that accurately measure what the customer wants, but which he is unable to quantify. What can we measure about engineered systems and about materials with respect to their "recyclability"?

Figure 4 Levels and categories of recycling

Not surprisingly, many of the most apt metrics are economic. Disposal costs (positive or negative) will someday be a significant factor in automotive life cycle costs along with manufacturing costs, maintenance costs, financing, etc. Disposal costs are currently small enough that they have little impact on overall automotive life cycle costs. Thus, disposal issues have little impact on the automotive design process. As indicated earlier, this situation is changing worldwide. Recycling cost (such as heuristic 8 above) is potentially an important kind of metric for the design process.

The development of "degraded reuse factors" for materials systems or components could also prove useful. These metrics might be based upon the percent value reduction from use 'n' to use 'n + 1' of a given material or component, normalized for environmental recovery costs.

A "recycling index" such as the following might even be developed:

$$RI \text{ (recycling index)} = \frac{RC}{M_V + E_V} \quad (2)$$

where M_V is the cost of producing ($M_{rec} - M_{exp}$) from virgin material and E_V is the cost of producing ($E_{rec} - E_{exp}$) by conventional means. Once again, all quantities are in monetary units. Low values of RI would be desirable.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The current picture for composites in terms of materials disposal is mixed. Composites can help in terms of source reduction for automotive waste material. This advantage should be quantified. Also, a number of processes are in various stages of development that promise to reuse or return energy from composites. On the other hand, these processes are far from perfect. Composites thus remain among the most difficult materials

(technologically, economically, and in terms of end markets) to recycle. Those of us who believe in the many well-established benefits of composites must be careful, lest composites become a "one 'but' technology" (44), a technology that is so promising, 'but' for one serious drawback - an inability to deal with disposal issues.

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BIOGRAPHIES

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